

Syntheses of 2,6-Dimethyl-1,6-heptadien-3-yl Acetate and 2,6-Dimethyl-1,5-heptadien-3-yl Acetate

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THE comstock mealybug, *Pseudococcus comstocki* Kuwana is one of the most serious pest of apple, pear and other agricultural crops. Mori *et al.*^{1,2} isolated and characterised sex pheromones of this pest as 2,6-dimethyl-1,6-heptadien-3-yl acetate (**1a**) and 2,6-dimethyl-1,5-heptadien-3-yl acetate (**1b**). Compounds **1a** and **1b** have been found to be highly active in the laboratory as well as field tests^{1,2}. Literature⁴⁻⁸ records a number of syntheses for these compounds. We herein report a short and simple synthesis of **1a** and **1b** in good yields (Chart 1).

Carbinol (**2a**) was obtained via alkylation of β -methylallyl chloride with sodium diethylmalonate followed by decarboxylation and LAH reduction in dry ether. PCC oxidation⁹ of **2a** in dry CH_2Cl_2 afforded pure **3a** after chromatographic purification, which was subjected to Grignard reaction with 2-propenylmagnesium bromide in THF to furnish **4a**. Acetylation of **4a** with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$ gave **1a** after chromatographic purification over silica gel.

4-Methyl-3-penten-1-ol (**2b**) prepared via two steps sequence, viz. Wittig reaction of 1-tetrahydropyran-3-ylpropanal with isopropylidene triphenyl phosphorane in THF followed by dehydration of the resultant product with PTS/MeOH. Compound **2b** on oxidation with PCC in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 followed by Grignard reaction with isopropylmagnesium bromide yielded **4b** which was acetylated with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O/Py}$ to afford pure **1b** after column chromatography over silica gel. The spectral data of synthetic materials **1a** and **1b** agreed with those reported in the literature⁴⁻⁷.

Experimental

IR spectra (thin film) of compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr

spectra (CCl_4) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel (ASC, Bombay) impregnated with CaSO_4 was used for tlc. Unless otherwise stated all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

4-Methyl-4-penten-1-ol (3a) and 4-methyl-3-penten-1-ol (3b): To a stirred suspension of PCC (6.5 g, 20 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 containing fused sodium acetate (0.5 g, 7.5 mmol) at room temperature, was added the alcohol (**2a**; 1.5 g, 15 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (10 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h, then diluted with anhydrous ether (100 ml), decanted from gummy residue and passed through neutral alumina to furnish **3a** (0.98 g, 66.5%) (Found: C, 73.2; H, 10.3. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$ requires: C, 73.4; H, 10.2%); ν_{max} 3 090, 1 705, 1 670, 1 440, 1 260 and 900 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.8 (3H, s, $=\text{CCH}_3$), 3.4 (4H, t, CH_2CH_2), 4.9 (2H, s, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}$), 9.75 (1H, s, CHO); **3b** (Found: C, 73.3; H, 10.3. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$ requires: C, 73.5; H, 10.2%); ν_{max} 2 950, 1 710, 1 650, 1 460, 960, 870 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.5–1.7 (6H, d, $=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.9–2.0 (2H, m, H^a/H^b), 5.2 (1H, t, H^c), 9.8 (1H, s, CHO).

2,6-Dimethyl-1,6-heptadien-3-ol (4a) and 2,6-dimethyl-1,5-heptadien-3-ol (4b): To a ice-cooled solution of Grignard reagent (prepared from 0.24 g, 10 mmol Mg turnings and 0.120 g, 10 mmol 2-bromopropene in 60 ml dry THF) was added dropwise a solution of **3a** (0.98 g, 10 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) and the contents were left overnight. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with saturated NH_4Cl solution, extracted with ether and dried. Removal of solvent followed by column chromatography over neutral alumina gave pure **4a** (1.09 g, 78%) (tlc single spot) (Found: C, 77.0; H, 11.3. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires: C, 77.1; H, 11.4%); ν_{max} 3 400, 2 940, 1 450 and 900 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.8 (6H, s, 2 CH_3), 2.2 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 3.8 (2H, m, CHO), 4.6–4.9 (4H, s, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $=\text{CH}_2$); **4b** (Found: C, 77.0; H, 11.3. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires: C, 77.1; H, 11.4%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 400, 2 930, 1 650, 1 460, 970 and 810 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.2 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.5–

1.6 (6H, d, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1.8–1.9 (2H, m, H^a/H^b), 3.3 (1H, m, H^c), 4.4–5.2 (4H, m, H^d/H^e and H^f/H^g).

2,6-Dimethyl-1,6-heptadien-3-yl acetate (1a) and 2,6-dimethyl-1,5-heptadien-3-yl acetate (1b): A mixture of **4a** (0.87 g, 6.2 mmol), acetic anhydride (0.12 ml) and pyridine was stirred at room temperature for 12 h. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water, extracted with ether, washed with 5% NaHCO_3 and dried. The solvent was removed and the resulting solution was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether–ether (9 : 1) to give **1a** (0.88 g, 78%) (Found: C, 72.31; H, 10.03. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 72.52; H, 9.89%); ν_{max} 3 000, 1 740, 1 455, 1 380, 890 and 820 cm^{-1} ;

δ (CCl_4) 1.6 (6H, s, 2CH_3), 1.8–2.0 (4H, m, CH_2CH_2), 2.1 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.6–5.1 (5H, m, $\text{CH}_2=\text{C}$, $\text{CH}_2=\text{C}$ and $\text{CHO}-$); **1b** (Found: C, 72.4; H, 10.0. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 72.5; H, 9.8%); ν_{max} 2980, 2860, 1750, 1650, 1450, 960 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 1.3 (3H, bs, $\sphericalangle\text{CH}_2$), 1.5–1.7 (6H, d, $(\text{H}_2\text{C})_2\text{C}=\text{}$), 2.0 (3H, s, $\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3$), 2.2 (2H, t, $\text{>}\text{C}\text{<}$), 4.6–5.2 (4H, m, $\text{>}\text{C}\text{<}$ and $\begin{matrix} \text{OAO} \\ | \\ \text{H} \end{matrix}$ and $\begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ | \\ \text{OH}_2 \end{matrix}$).

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Preparation of some 1-Guanyl/(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles

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PYRAZOLE and isoxazole derivatives have been reported to possess various biological activities¹. The present communication deals with the preparation of some new pyrazole derivatives of type **1b** with an intention to synthesise biologically active products.

Substituted benzene diazonium chloride was condensed with acetoacetanilide to get **1a**. The product was refluxed with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine or aminoguanidine nitrate in acetic acid to get **1b**. The structural assignments of the products were

based on their elemental analysis and uv, ir and pmr spectral data.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a specord Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 instrument using TMS as an internal standard. All the melting points are uncorrected.

2-Arylhydrazono-1-phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione^a: Appropriate aniline (0.01 mol) was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 ml) and water (4 ml) and the solution was cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To it, an ice-cooled aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.7 g) was added in small portions. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into already cooled mixture of acetoacetanilide (0.01 mol), sodium acetate (8.0 g) and water (25 ml) with stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from water–dimethylformamide mixture, m.p. 110° (Found: N, 14.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: N, 14.94%); M^+ at m/e 281.

Nmr spectra of **1a** revealed signals at δ 2.6 ± 0.06 (COCH_3), 12.90–13.50 (broad, $\text{NH}-(-\text{NH}-\text{N}=\text{C})$), and 7.00–8.20 (ArH for two phenyl rings). It appears that the small shift of the CH_3 signal to lower field is due to the hydrogen bonding and therefore the following are the correct structures for these compounds.

